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Cost-effective, fast and easy detection of *Polymyxa graminis* and of the viruses it transmits to cereal crops

Cereal crops serve as the primary food source worldwide. In order to meet the UN sustainable development goal on zero hunger, it is essential to protect cereals from the threat posed by pests.

The CEREVER project aimed to expand knowledge on the current occurrence of cereal viruses through a partnership between the scientists involved in the Euphresco project and CGIAR Plant Health Initiative organizations from important cereal crop-growing areas. Additionally, the CEREVER project aimed to improve the diagnosis of several highly damaging viruses.

Image by Hans from Pixabay

Soil-borne viruses transmitted by the plasmodiophorid *P. graminis* have been known for a long time but still pose a significant threat to cereal crops. *P. graminis* is an obligate biotrophic root parasite that forms spores containing viruses. Such spores can persist in soil for many years. The zoospores infect host root cells, where they multiply. During the infection process, the viruses contained in the spores can be transmitted and subsequently systemically infect the host plants, causing diseases.

One of the objectives of the project was to improve the monitoring of *Polymyxa graminis*-transmitted soilborne viruses infecting wheat and other small grain cereal crops. This is especially crucial due to climate change as increased temperatures and extreme weather events stress plants and may weaken plant resilience to biotic stress.

During the project, a new test based on isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP) was developed for easy and cost-effective detection of the soil-borne cereal mosaic virus directly from crude plant material extracts. Until now, real-time RT-PCR and ELISA tests were available, but their limitations in terms of costs, labour, and sensitivity hindered extensive surveys on virus prevalence.

The RT-LAMP test developed during the project has several advantages: it does not require any extraction step, it provides results rapidly, and it has shown high sensitivity. The sensitivity and specificity of the developed RT-LAMP protocol are comparable to the existing real-time RT-PCR tests, with the obvious advantage that RT-LAMP produces results in minutes rather than hours (Marra *et al.* 2022). The availability of this new diagnostic tool paves the way for extensive field surveys, leading to a better knowledge of the impact of soil-borne cereal mosaic virus on wheat health and yield.

A similar test is being developed for another important virus, wheat spindle streak mosaic virus (WSSMV). Additionally, a set of quantitative real-time PCR tests is being developed to detect soil-borne cereal mosaic virus, soil-borne wheat mosaic virus and Japanese soil-borne wheat mosaic virus RNA1 and RNA2. These tests will facilitate the monitoring of the viruses and will help answer questions regarding their spread.

The tests developed within the framework of the CEREVER project will greatly facilitate the monitoring of countries, especially those for which no data for *P. polymyxa*-transmitted virus presence is available. Knowledge of the occurrence and spread of the *P. graminis*-transmitted cereal viruses will increase, which will allow countries to be better prepared against the current and future threats posed by these viruses.

Project ID: Diagnosis and epidemiology of viruses infecting cereal crops (CEREVER).

Reference: Marra *et al.* (2022) Fast and sensitive detection of soil-borne cereal mosaic virus in leaf crude extract of durum wheat. *Viruses* 15:140. doi: 10.3390/v15010140